

Isotopic Exchange and Racemisation of Some β -Diketonato Complexes

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KINETICS of substitution reactions of metal complexes have drawn the attention of many chemists in these two or three decades. Taube first proposed to classify metal complexes according to the rate of their substitution reactions, *i.e.* substitution labile and substitution inert¹. Mechanism of substitution reactions has been mostly studied with substitution inert complexes, *e.g.* those of cobalt(III), chromium(III) and rhodium(III) with octahedral structure and of palladium(II), rhodium(I) and platinum(II) with square planer structure. Most typical elements give substitution labile complexes, and the knowledge relating to their substitution mechanism is far less.

Substitution reaction in water is definitely most important, because water is the most common solvent and many reactions of our major interest takes place in water. However, water is a powerful ligand for various metal ions and overwhelms other ligands in its concentration. Hence the aqueous system is not a convenient medium in discussing the kinetics and mechanism of substitution reactions involving other ligands. Information concerning reaction kinetics in non-aqueous solvents is, however, much less².

Isotopic exchange and racemisation are those reactions in which no net chemical reaction is involved. They are studied in chemically equilibrated state and the rate can be a good measure of the lability and the general dynamic properties of given compounds. Isotopic exchange was first kinetically treated by McKay in 1939³. When two compounds A (molar concentration a) and B (b) containing m and n moles of exchanging species, respectively, undergo isotopic exchange, the rate is expressed by equation 1.

$$R = -2.303 \cdot (ma \cdot nb / (ma + nb)) (\log[1 - F] / t) \quad (1)$$

where t is the lapse of time and F the fraction of reaction. By use of a radioisotope, F is written as

x_i/x_∞ where x_i and x_∞ are the specific activity of A (or B) at time i and infinity, respectively. The R is not a rate constant but a function of a and b . Examination of the relationship between R and a and b reveals the reaction kinetics and thus the reaction mechanism can be discussed.

The present author found that when typical metal ions such as gallium(III) and indium(III) are chelated with multidentate ligands such as EDTA, their isotopic exchange with aquo metal ions was extremely slow, and reported detailed kinetics by use of their radioisotopes⁴. It was thus demonstrated that even "substitution labile" ions can give slow reaction kinetics, whenever they are chelated with multidentate ligands. It would be most interesting, if an appropriate system were found in which both labile and inert metal complexes are mutually compared.

Acetylacetone (2,4-pentanedione; Hacac) is one of the most common bidentate ligands and its enol form gives anions $acac^-$ with a pK_a *ca.* 11 in water. Bis-, tris- and tetrakis-complexes with six-membered chelate rings are known with a variety of metal ions and very often they are chargeless. This β -diketone has many homologues in which 2- and 3-positions are replaced by other groups. Their enol forms give anions with different pK_a 's depending on the nature of the substituting groups.

Isotopic exchange of some β -diketonato complexes in organic solvents.

Tervalent cations give one to three complexes with various β -diketonates which are soluble in organic solvents. The isotopic exchange between $(M(acac)_3)^0$ and Hacac-C¹⁴ was first examined by Kluiber in 1960⁵. He gave approximate percentage of exchange of several complexes within 10 min. in concentrated chloroform and dioxane solutions.

We found that most of chargeless β -diketonato complexes are insoluble in petroleum ether, and recovered crystalline free from excessive ligand by adding the mixture of the complex with the ligand in organic solvents into chilled petroleum ether.⁶ A known amount of the crystalline complex is dissolved in a liquid scintillation counter and submitted to the measurement of specific activity. We have extended the kinetic studies since 1965 and discussed the mechanism of isotopic exchange. The contribution of various terms upon the rate of exchange is tabulated in Table 1. As shown in the following, typical elements give slow isotopic exchange under certain conditions and seems to involve dissociative mechanism. Their characteristics are compared with those of transition metal β -diketonates.

TABLE 1. INFLUENCE OF VARIOUS FACTORS ON THE ISOTOPIC EXCHANGE RATE OF VARIOUS ACETYLACETONATO COMPLEXES

Ion	Solvent	k_1	[H ₂ O]	[acid]	[ligand]	Ref.
Al(III)	Polar	O	O	O	X	6
	non-polar	X	O	O	X	6
Ga(III)	polar	Δ	O	O	O	7
Pd(II)	non-polar	O	X	O	O	8
Co(III)	non-polar	O	X	X	O	9
Be(II)	both	O	—	—	O	10

O, contribution appreciable ; X, contribution not appreciable ; Δ , contribution uncertain ; —, not examined.

Details of individual experimental results have been published elsewhere, and here some typical kinetics are shown as examples. The β -diketonato complexes do not undergo any chemical change under the given experimental conditions and McKay plots are linear for several half periods except for the cobalt(III) complex, which gives linear McKay plots only in the initial stage of exchange.

The exchange of Al and Ga complexes is catalysed by water. Too high a concentration of water results in hydrolysis, but in the given concentration ranges the diagrams are linear. Figures 1 to 4 give the results. Whilst the exchange of [Ga(acac)₃] and [Al(acac)₃] in polar solvents such as ethylacetate and tetrahydrofuran gives intercepts, that of [Al(acac)₃] in toluene and of [Al(dbm)₃] (dbm⁻ stands for the anion of dibenzoylmethane in enol form) in tetrahydrofuran does not. The exchange of Al and Ga

Fig. 1. Relationship between k_0 and water concentration for [Al(acac)₃] in ethylacetate (A, B, C) and tetrahydrofuran (D). A 0°C, B 30°C, C 35°C, D 25°C.

Fig. 2. Relationship between k_0 and water concentration for [Ga(acac)₃] in tetrahydrofuran. A 0°C, B 10°C, C 20°C, [Hacac]=0.070 M ; D, 0°C, [Hacac]=0.070 M, [trichloroacetic acid]=0.0029 M.

complexes is catalysed by acids, and the extent of catalytic action depends on water concentration as Figs. 2 and 5 illustrate. In all the systems the

Fig. 3. Relationship between k_0 and water concentration for $[\text{Al}(\text{acac})_3]$ in toluene (A, B, C) and xylene (D). A, 0°C ; B, 25°C ; C, 35°C ; D, 25°C in three isomers of xylene. Open marks, $[\text{Hacac}] = 0.070 \text{ M}$; full marks, $[\text{Hacac}]$ varying.

Fig. 4. Relationship between k_0 and water concentration for $[\text{Al}(\text{dbm})_3]$ in tetrahydrofuran. A 30°C , B 40°C , C 50°C ; $[\text{Hacac}] = 0.050 \text{ M}$.

Fig. 5. Influence of water upon the exchange rate of $[\text{Al}(\text{dbm})_3]$ (A, B, C, D) and $[\text{Al}(\text{acac})_3]$ (E) in the presence of acid. A, 30°C , B 40°C , C 50°C in tetrahydrofuran $[\text{trichloroacetic acid}] = 0.029 \text{ M}$; D 40°C in tetrahydrofuran, $[\text{acid}] = 0.0021 \text{ M}$; E 25°C in toluene, $[m\text{-toluic acid}] = 0.090 \text{ M}$.

exchange rate R is proportional to the concentration of the complex. The influence of ligand concentration is shown in Figs. 6 to 8. Trisacetylacetonato-aluminium fails to give the influence, but other com-

plexes give ligand dependent term, although the extent is very different. Figures 7 clearly indicates that the diagrams are parallel to one another and the water- and the ligand-dependent term operate individually.

Fig. 6. Influence of ligand concentration upon the exchange rate of $[\text{Al}(\text{acac})_3]$ (A, B) and $[\text{Al}(\text{dbm})_3]$ (C, D). A 35°C in toluene; B 25°C in ethylacetate; C 40°C and D 50°C in tetrahydrofuran.

Fig. 7. Influence of ligand concentration upon the exchange rate of $[\text{Ga}(\text{acac})_3]$ in tetrahydrofuran. 0°C ; $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, A 0.029, B 0.036, C 0.043, D 0.050 M.

Fig. 8. Influence of ligand concentration upon the exchange rate of $[Co(acac)_3]$ at an early stage. (90°C)

Since isotopic exchange cannot take place in the absence of the ligand, it is senseless to discuss the intercept of the diagrams; however it represents the rate in an extremely low concentration of the ligand. A small amount of water (less than $10^{-3}M$) cannot be removed from the system, and the essential part of the present isotopic exchange is expressed by the following rate formula,

$$R = [\text{complex}] (k_1 + k_2 [H_2O] + k_3 [\text{ligand}]) \quad (2)$$

In the presence of acid, acid-catalysed path is added, which consists of two terms, one independent and the other dependent on the water concentration: $k_4[\text{acid}] + k'[\text{acid}][H_2O]$. The data for the aluminium and gallium complexes are summarised in Table 2. As seen in Table 1, some of the terms

TABLE 2. RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE ISOTOPIC EXCHANGE OF $[Al(acac)_3]$, $[Al(dbm)_3]$ AND $[Ga(acac)_3]$ IN ORGANIC SOLVENTS. (25°)

$$\text{Rate} = [\text{complex}] (k_1 + k_2 [H_2O] + k_3 [\text{ligand}] + k_4 [\text{acid}] + k'_4 [\text{acid}][H_2O])$$

Complex	$[Al(acac)_3]$		$[Al(dbm)_3]^a$		$[Ga(acac)_3]^b$
	Ethyl-acetate	Toluene	Tetrahydrofuran		
$k_1/10^{-6}s^{-1}$	1.1	0	1.0	0	1
$k_2/10^{-4}M^{-1}s^{-1}$	4.6	26.7	3.3	0.32	3.1
$k_3/10^{-5}M^{-1}s^{-1}$	0	0	0	c	7.1
$k_4/10^{-4}M^{-1}s^{-1}$ d	9.0	15.8	1.55	0.20	14.8
$k'_4/10^{-2}M^{-2}s^{-1}$ d	5.0	21.7	2.0	0.09 e	4.1
$\Delta H^\ddagger /kcal.mol^{-1}$ f	21.4	19.2	21.4	25.6	17

(a) k values converted into those at 25°C with the aid of ΔH^\ddagger

(b) k values at 0°C. (c) very small but appreciable. (d) *m*-toluic acid for $[Al(acac)_3]$ and trichloroacetic acid for $[Al(dbm)_3]$ and $[Ga(acac)_3]$.

(e) at a very low concentration of water and acid.

(f) practically equal for all the paths.

Fig. 9. Plausible reaction mechanism for the isotopic exchange of $[M(\text{acac})_3]$ in organic solvents. Capital K 's, equilibrium constants; small k 's rate constants at the rate-determining step; arcs anions of β -diketones in enol form; S, solvent molecule.

are missing in certain systems. However, the overall reaction mechanism is understood as shown in Fig. 9.

Reaction mechanism: A characteristic feature of the present systems is that the ΔH^\ddagger values for various terms are practically equal for a given system. (Some of the k 's were obtained by extrapolation and their activation parameters may involve bigger errors.)

Whenever a bidentate ligand is replaced, there are two possible rate-determining steps. One is the break of the first bond of a chelate so that the second bond breaks rapidly. The other mechanism presumes a rapid equilibrium between the bidentate and the unidentate state of a ligand and reckons the break of the second bond as rate-determining. In the present systems the second mechanism seems to be more appropriate. The catalytic action of water and acid are understood by considering that they occupy the vacant co-ordination site of the intermediate and the free end of the unidentate ligand, respectively, to retard the recombination of the unidentate ligand. The fact that the activation enthalpies are equal for all the kinetic terms will be accounted for by that such occupations would affect the break of the remaining bond less. If the break of the first bond were the rate-determining step, catalytic action by water or acid would bring about larger difference in ΔH^\ddagger values.

The influence of the free ligand can be either understood by considering a similar occupation of

the vacant co-ordination site or a rather associative nature. It is rather difficult at the present stage to distinguish the two possible ways. Smaller ΔH^\ddagger values for the gallium complex may favour the associative, S_N2 -like attack by the free ligand. However, this can take place either on the complex itself or on the intermediate with a one-ended ligand.

The two terms for acid catalysis may represent two possible proton carriers. In the k_4 term the acid itself will be proton carrier and in the k_4' term proton is transferred to water molecule as follows.

Different carriers, however, give up proton for the free end of the unidentate ligand as shown in Fig. 9. When the equilibrium and the rate constant are designated as in Fig. 9, the observed kinetic terms are expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} k_1 &= k_s K_u K_s & k_2 &= k_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} K_u K_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \\ k_4 &= k_{\text{H}^-} K_u K_{\text{acid}} & k_4' &= k_{\text{H}^+} K_u K_{\text{H}_2\text{O}^+} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

They all consist of more than one constant, but the temperature co-efficient of rate constants (small k 's) will overwhelm that of equilibrium constants, and the observed ΔH^\ddagger values will represent those for k 's.

Square planer complex: The isotopic exchange of $[\text{Pd}(\text{acac})_2]$ was studied in some solvents. The

exchange rate R is proportional to the complex concentration and the influence of the ligand concentration (k_o vs. $[\text{ligand}]$, where $k_o = R/[\text{complex}]$) is illustrated in Fig. 10. The acid catalysis is shown in Fig. 11, which clearly indicates that the ligand concentration and the acid concentration give independent contribution of each other. Hence the rate is expressed by equation 4. Water does not affect the exchange rate.

$$R = [\text{complex}] (k_1 + k_3 [\text{ligand}] + k_4 [\text{acid}]) \quad (4)$$

Fig. 10. Influence of ligand concentration of upon the exchange rate of $[\text{Pd}(\text{acac})_2]$ in organic solvents, 60°C ; A, 1, 2-dichloroethane; B anisole; C benzene.

Fig. 11. Influence of ligand concentration upon the exchange rate of $[\text{Pd}(\text{acac})_2]$ in the presence of acids in anisole. A, 0.00024 M *m*-toluic acid; B, 0.00025 M *o*-bromobenzoic acid; C, 0.0050 M *m*-toluic acid. 60°C .

When the concentration of acid overwhelms, the exchange apparently proceeds without being influenced by ligand; *i.e.* the contribution of k_2 term is negligible.

It is generally understood that the k_1 term represents the "solvent path," in which the solvent molecule gives $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ attack on the square planer complex. In our present system, however, the intercepts of Fig. 10 are almost equal to one another regardless of the nature of the solvent. It is likely that the k_1 term is rather dissociative in nature than "solvent path".

Complexes of silicon(IV) and germanium(IV): These ions give one to three complexes with β -diketones such as $[\text{Si}(\text{acac})_3]^+$ and $[\text{Ge}(\text{acac})_3]^+$. Isotopic exchange of their perchlorates in organic solvents (acetonitrile and tetrachloroethane) is extremely slow below 80°C .^{11, 12}

Other complexes—Titanium(IV) gives acetylacetonato complexes such as $[\text{Ti}(\text{acac})_3]^+$ and $[\text{TiCl}_2(\text{acac})_2]$.¹³ The isotopic exchange of the former with Hacac-C^{14} is fast but can be measured below 0°C . The rate is largely dependent on the ligand concentration and seems to be rather associative in nature.¹⁴

The isotopic exchange of indium(III) complexes such as $[\text{In}(\text{dbm})_3]$ is much faster than that of the gallium complex in the same solvent. Its acetylacetonato complex undergoes hydrolysis even in carefully dehydrated organic solvents containing *ca.* 10^{-3} M water, and the isotopic exchange cannot be followed.⁷

The rate for the chromium(III) complex is measurable over 140 and 180°C in organic solvents and gaseous phase, respectively.

Racemisation of β -diketonato complexes.

Among various tris- β -diketonato complexes of trivalent metal ions, only chromium(III), cobalt(III),¹⁵ rhodium(III),¹⁶ gadolinium(III) and yttrium(III)¹⁷ have been partially resolved. Their racemisation was studied little¹⁸. Most information related to their racemisation comes from n.m.r. studies of "site exchange" of tris- β -diketonato complexes with asymmetric β -diketones such as benzoylacetone and trifluoroacetylacetone.¹⁹ These ligands give geometrical isomers, *mer* and *fac*, and the proton signals for them differ from each other. By examining the change of half width values of the signals or the coalescence, interchange of the co-ordination sites

TABLE 3. RATE OF RACEMISATION OF $[\text{Si}(\text{ACAC})_3]^+$, $[\text{Si}(\text{DBM})_3]^+$ AND $[\text{Ge}(\text{ACAC})_3]^+$ IN ORGANIC SOLVENTS.

Solvents	tetrachloroethane			acetonitrile	
	$[\text{Si}(\text{acac})_3]^-$	$[\text{Si}(\text{dbm})_3]^-$	$[\text{Si}(\text{acac})_3]^-$	$[\text{Si}(\text{dbm})_3]^+$	$[\text{Ge}(\text{acac})_3]^+$
k_1/s^{-1} a	9.5×10^{-7}	5.1×10^{-6} b	1.1×10^{-5}	1.6×10^{-5}	8.0×10^{-6}
$k_2/M^{-1}s^{-1}$ a	3.6×10^{-5} c	2.3×10^{-5} bc	6.5×10^{-2} d	0 e	9.0×10^{-5} e
$\Delta H^\ddagger / \text{kcal.mol}^{-1}$	(k_1)	31.6 ± 0.1	32.4 ± 0.6	25.7 ± 0.2	24.2 ± 1.0
	(k_2)	29.3 ± 1.9	25.0 ± 0.7	ca. 18	23.0 ± 1.1
$\Delta S^\ddagger / \text{cal.K}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$	(k_1)	14.6	14.3	0.53	-4.5
	(k_2)	14.2	-5.1	-5.8	-3.5

(a) all the complexes are as perchlorate, at 40° C except for b. (b) at 60° C. (c) acid catalysis with trichloroacetic acid.
 (d) base catalysis with 2, 6-lutidine ; k_2 for pyridine is $1.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ at 40° C. (e) base catalysis with pyridine.

can be studied. The site exchange involves both isomerisation and racemisation, and it is generally believed that they proceed intra-molecularly, presumably through an intermediate with one unidentate ligand.*

Resolution and racemisation of tris- β -diketonato silicon(IV) and germanium(IV)—The silicon complex was first resolved by Kirschner and his co-workers. They studied the racemisation in water and some alcohols, and claimed that it involved solvolysis or hydrolysis.²² Further studies by Pearson *et al.*²³ and Muetterties *et al.*²⁴ disclosed that intrinsic racemisation is also taking place, but the evidence was rather indirect.

We have resolved homologous compounds $[\text{Si}(\text{dbm})_3]^{+11}$ and $[\text{Ge}(\text{acac})_3]^{+12}$ by a similar method to that for $[\text{Si}(\text{acac})_3]^+$. It was found that $[\text{Si}(\text{acac})_3]\text{ClO}_4$, $[\text{Si}(\text{dbm})_3]\text{ClO}_4$ and $[\text{Ge}(\text{acac})_3]\text{ClO}_4$ undergo intrinsic racemisation in carefully dehydrated organic solvents without involved in solvolysis or hydrolysis. Figure 12 shows the change of optical rotation at Na D line and of extinction at 305 nm (absorption peak) of $[\text{Si}(\text{acac})_3]^+$ in tetrachloroethane with time. The racemisation rate was

* α -Diketones such as tropolone derivatives also give tris-type complexes with a variety of metal ions. Their site exchange has been widely studied similarly.²⁰ It is claimed that they proceed *via* intra-molecular mechanism but without bond break (trigonal twist). The reason is that tropolone derivatives have rather rigid planer structure and the unidentate form will have very short lives. Further, semi-empirical calculation disclosed that the intermediate, trigonal prism, of tris- α -diketonato complexes is much more stable than that of tris- β -diketonato complexes.²¹

Fig. 12. Change of optical rotation at NaD line (A) and of extinction at 305 nm (B) of $[\text{Si}(\text{acac})_3]\text{ClO}_4$ in tetrachloroethane.

measured at varying temperatures and the results are shown in Table 3.

The rate is not affected by the concentration of free ligand and water under the given conditions. Acid catalysis is observed in tetrachloroethane with trichloroacetic acid, and base catalysis operates in acetonitrile with pyridine bases. In low concentration regions, the catalytic action linearly increases with increase in acid or base concentration, so that the following equation holds :

$$k_0 = k_1 + k_2 [\text{acid or base}] \quad (5)$$

The k_2 values and the corresponding activation parameters are included in Table 3.

Fig. 13. Plausible reaction mechanism of racemisation of tris- β -diketonatosilicon(IV) in organic solvents.

Since the inter-molecular isotopic exchange is very slow and no net chemical change is involved, the racemisation definitely proceeds *via* an intra-molecular mechanism. Such a change can take place either with or without break of one metal-ligand bond. We consider that the present racemisation proceeds *via* an intermediate with a unidentate ligand from the following reasons. A twist mechanism without bond break^{25, 26} will be less sensitive towards acid or base catalysis.

Two possible rate-determining steps can be encountered, whenever an intermediate with one unidentate ligand is involved. One is to reckon the bond break to give the intermediate as rate-determining and the probability of intra-molecular rearrangement is expressed by equation 6. (see Fig. 13)

$$k_1 = k_b k_{sy} / (k_{-b} + k_{sy}) \quad (6)$$

An alternative is to consider that one of the bonds of a given ligand breaks and forms quickly and the rearrangement is the rate-determining step.

Table 4 shows the change of k_1 of various tris- β -diketonatosilicon(IV) in tetrachloroethane. Introduction of ethyl and phenyl at R and R' in place of methyl decreases the rate slightly. The pK_a values of the ligands increase in the same order and the slowing-down will be related to the stronger Si-O bond. The pK_a values of the R''-substituted ligands are bigger than Hacac and slower racemisation might have been expected. The rapid racemisation must be related to favourable rearrangement of the unidentate

ligand. These β -diketones are claimed to have more stable *trans*-R'R'' isomer than *cis* in the enol form and the isomerisation is quick.²⁷ If the unidentate ligand assumes a similar state to free enol, it is likely that introduction of methyl on R'' will make the recombination of the free end more difficult. The bigger k_1 will be due to increase in the $k_{sy} / (k_{-b} + k_{sy})$.

TABLE 4. RATE OF RACEMISATION OF SUBSTITUTED β -DIKETONATO COMPLEXES OF SILICON(IV) IN TETRACHLOROETHANE. (50°)

R	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅
R'	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅
R''	H	H	H	CH ₃	CH ₃
$k_1/10^{-6}s^{-1}$	4.8	1.8	1.1	88	45
ΔH^\ddagger /kcal.mol ⁻¹	31.6	32.7	32.4	25.2	25.0
ΔS^\ddagger /cal.K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	+15	+16	+14	+0.6	-0.8

R,R' : substituents on carbonyl carbon. R'' : substituents on γ .

Table 5 gives the solvent effect on the racemisation of [Ge(acac)₃]⁺. Despite of similar dielectric constant and dipole moment, nitromethane gives smaller k_1 than acetonitrile. Gutmann's donor number (D.N.)²⁸ can be a good measure for the k_1 's. It reflects the ease for the solvent molecule to squeeze in the coordination sphere to facilitate the bond break.

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 TABLE 5. RATE OF RECEMISATION OF $[\text{Ge}(\text{ACAC})_3]\text{ClO}_4$ IN VARIOUS ORGANIC SOLVENTS. (50°)

Solvent	$\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{Cl}_4$	CH_3NO_2	CH_3CN	DMF
Dielectric constant	8.2	35.8	37.5	36.7
Dipole moment μ/Debye	1.85	3.17	3.44	3.86
Donor number ²⁸		2.7	14.1	27
$k_1/10^{-5}\text{s}^{-1}$	0.4	0.42	2.8	10
$\Delta H^\ddagger/\text{kcal.mol}^{-1}$	31	26.5	24.7	23

From these reasons we think that the present racemisation proceeds with a unidentate form as intermediate and the break of the M-O bond is the rate determining-step. In this context the rate can be compared with that of similar complexes of trivalent metal ions measured as site-exchange.

Comparison of the lability of acetylacetonato complexes in related reactions

The following sequence gives the overall order of lability of some metal ions, both typical and transition towards isotopic exchange.

The detailed mechanism of their inter-molecular isotopic exchange differs from one another as mentioned before. The sequence, however, gives a general idea related to their labilities. It is rather marked that so-called substitution labile ions can give slow reaction rate under certain conditions. Some of the complexes have dominating associative route for isotopic exchange, and the sequence does not necessarily reflect the ease of bond break of metal ligand bond. Nevertheless a remarkable influence of the charge is seen.

The sequence 8 gives the order of lability towards intra-molecular site exchange including racemisation and isomerisation.

Individual data of site exchange have been obtained by various workers under varying conditions, and the comparison should remain approximate.*

We have discussed that the isotopic exchange of the β -diketonato complexes in sequence 7 has a rate-determining step at the break of the second metal-ligand bond. On the other hand, the site exchange (sequence 8) involves rate-determining steps at the break of first metal-ligand bond. These two sequences are similar to each other in most part, indicating a dominating effect of the charge of the metal ions. However, β -diketonato complexes of quadrivalent silicon and germanium give smaller rate of inter-molecular exchange and larger rate of intra-molecular site-exchange than those of trivalent cobalt. (Inertness of chromium(III) may be interpreted by the big affinity towards oxygen in general.) This fact may suggest a ruling influence of the charge of metal ions particularly upon the strength of single metal—ligand bond in the intermediate with a unidentate ligand.

The studies are the joint work with my co-workers, whose names are seen in the references. We are very grateful to Nishina Memorial Foundation and Ministry of Education of Japanese Government for generous grant in aid. Thanks are also due to the Indian Chemical Society to have provided a chance to give a plenary lecture in such a commemoration meeting.

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* The fact that site exchange is always faster than isotopic exchange for a given complex, gives further support that the rate-determining step of the latter reaction is the break of the second metal-ligand bond of β -diketonate.

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